

FRACTIONAL DISTRIBUTION OF SOIL CONTAMINATED WITH LEAD NITRATE AND CADMIUM NITRATE USING SEQUENTIAL EXTRACTION METHOD

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Abstract

A separate pot experiment was conducted to compare the metal uptake of soil spiked with amount of lead nitrate (Pb₀- 0 mg/kg, Pb₁- 1000 mg/kg, Pb₂- 500 mg/kg, Pb₃- 250 mg/kg, Pb₄- 125 mg/kg, Pb₅- 62.5 mg/kg), cadmium nitrate (Cd₀- 0 mg/kg, Cd₁- 1000 mg/kg, Cd₂- 500 mg/kg, Cd₃- 250 mg/kg, Cd₄- 12.5 mg/kg, Cd₅- 62.5 mg/kg) and the combination of the two salts using maize plant. The experiment was carried out under a greenhouse condition for ten weeks; the maize cob was harvested and analysed with Atomic Absorption Spectroscopic (AAS). Sequential extraction was used to fractionate the spiked soils into five operationally defined groups: Exchangeable, Carbonate, Fe-Mn oxide, Organic and residual. The Organic fraction was the most abundant pool for the soil spiked with lead nitrate while Carbonate is the most abundant for that spiked with cadmium nitrate and the results obtained from the combination of the two salts indicated that Organic fraction was the most abundant. Metal distribution in the different chemical fractions in these soils depends on the respective total metal concentration used to spike the soil.

Key words: Fraction, Maize, Sorghum, Cassava, Rice, Lead, Cadmium, Spiked

INTRODUCTION

Soil, which comprised of detritus, inorganic or organic particles, is relatively heterogeneous in terms of its physical, chemical and biological characteristics (Hakanson, 1992). Heavy metals are associated with various soil components in different ways, and these associations determine their mobility and availability (Ahumuda, *et al.*; 1999). Water soluble and exchangeable forms are considered readily mobile and crystalline lattice of clays appear relatively inactive. The other forms like carbonate bound, occlusion in Fe, Mn and Al oxides, or complexes with organic matter and Fe-Mn oxides have been found to be the most important in soil and might be the components, which influence the medium to long term effect on lability and bioavailability of metals (Iyenger, *et al.*, 1981 and Karczewska, *et al.*, 1998).

In recent years studies on the speciation or chemical forms of heavy metals in polluted soil

using sequential techniques have increased, because these provide knowledge on metal affinity to soil components and the strength with which they are bound to the Matrix (Narwal, *et al.*, 1999).

Numerous extraction schemes have been described in the literature (Chao, 1972; Clevenger, 1990; Sposito, *et al.*, 1982; Howard, *et al.*, 1999; Tessier, *et al.* 1979; Ure, *et al.*, 1983 and Welt, *et al.*, 1983). The procedure of Tessier, *et al.*, (1979) is one of the most thoroughly researched and widely used procedures to evaluate the possible chemical associations of metal in sediments and soils. In this method, metal distribution is studied through five major geochemical forms:

1. Exchangeable phase.
2. Bound to carbonate phase
3. Bound to Fe-Mn oxides

4. Bound to organic matter
5. Residual metal phase.

However, the limitations of chemical extraction methods have also been addressed (Jonanneau *et al.*, 1983, Khebonien and Bauer, 1987; Quevauviller, *et al.* 1997; Rauret, *et al.*, 1989 and Rauret, *et al.*, 1999). The limitations include technical difficulties associated with selective dissolution and complete recovery of trace metal from chemical phases in soil and sediments. Therefore, the chemical forms of heavy metals from the sequential extraction methods are operationally defined phases only. The aim of this study was to investigate the different chemical forms of heavy metals in the soil spiked with lead nitrate, cadmium nitrate and the combination of the two salts and to also reveal the uptake of lead and cadmium by maize cob.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Soil was collected from a semi-forest which was dried thereafter was processed for analysis. 1 kg of the processed soil was weighed into 15 different pots and kept in the green house. 5 of the 15 pots with the processed soil were treated treated/spiked 100 mg, 500 mg, 250 mg, 125 mg, and 62.5 mg of Lead Nitrate same was done with 1000 mg, 500 mg, 250 mg, 125 mg, and 62.5 mg of Cadmium Nitrate for another different 5 pots while a combination of equal amount of Cadmium and Lead Nitrate was also used treat/spike the processed soil in the remaining 5 pots to compare the uptake if the two heavy metal are together.

Three seeds of 0.5g of white maize was planted or sown on the 15 different pots containing the spiked soil and the soil was watered with deionized water and left to grow though the plant was watered every morning under

greenhouse condition. In the three categories, there is a control attached in which the heavy metal is not added to the processed soil.

After 10 weeks, the maize cob was harvested and then sun dried for some days, after which it was placed in an oven at 250 °C for 30 mins which was followed by pulverization process.

1 g of the pulverized sample was weighed accurately in a platinum crucible, ashed at 450 °C- 500°C and then allowed to room temperature in a desicator. The ash was dissolved in a 10ml of concentrated nitric acid and the solution was carefully transferred through a filter paper into a 100ml volumetric flask. The crucible was well rinsed with deionised water and transferred to the flask, and make up to mark with deionized water and shaken to mix well. The 18 different pots were prepared in a similar manner and sent for Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometry (AAS) while the physical-chemical properties of the soil were determined using a standard method. Each soil spiked was fractionated following a modification of the sequential extraction procedure to determine the metal binding forms (Khebonien and Bauer, 1987). By this procedure, variation of these metals in five binding phases (exchangeable, bound to carbonates, bound to Fe-Mn oxides, bound to organic and the residual form were determined. The separation extraction procedures are as follows:

EXCHANGEABLE: - Soil (1g dry weight) was extract with 20 ml of 1M NH₄OAC (pH-7.0) in Teflon centrifuge tubes for 30 min. with continuous agitation.

BOUND TO CARBONATE: - The residue from exchangeable fraction was extracted with 20 ml of 1M NAOAC (pH- 5.0 adjusted with HOAC) for 5 hrs. with continuous agitation.

BOUND TO Fe-Mn OXIDE: - The residue from the carbonate fraction was continuously extracted with 20 ml of 0.4 M NH₂OH.HCL in 25 % acetic acid for 6 hrs. with continuous agitation at 96⁰ C.

BOUND TO ORGANIC MATTER: - The residue from the Fe-Mn oxide fraction was extracted with 5ml of 0.02 M HNO₃ and 10 ml of 30 % H₂O₂ adjusted to pH 2 with concentrated HNO₃. The mixture was heated to 85 % for 2 hrs. with occasional agitation. A second 6 ml aliquot of 30 % H₂O₂ (pH 2 with concentration HNO₃) was the added and the

sample was heated again to 85⁰ C for 3 hrs. with intermittent agitation.

RESIDUAL: - The residue from the organic matter fraction was digested with a mixture of concentrated HNO₃ and HClO₄ for 6 hrs. until the appearance of white fumes. The residue was dissolved in 12 M HCL and diluted to 25 ml following each extraction, mixture were centrifuged at 1200 rpm for 30 min. prior to the start of the next extraction step, the residues were shaken with 8 ml deionized water for 30 min, centrifuged and the extracted solutions discharged. The various filtrates were analyzed for Pb and Cd.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Result of fraction of soil spiked with lead nitrate

S/N	SPIKED SOIL (mg/kg)	EXCHANGEABLE (mg/kg)	CARBONATE (mg/kg)	Fe-Mn OXIDE (mg/kg)	ORGANIC MATTER (mg/kg)	RESIDUAL (mg/kg)	TOTAL FRACTION (mg/kg)
1	Pb ₀	BDL	BDL	BDL	0.17	BDL	0.17
2	Pb ₁	125.15	193.04	186.95	338.20	113.11	956.45
3	Pb ₂	103.45	57.00	87.23	166.17	44.86	458.71
4	Pb ₃	50.58	59.83	11.65	82.40	20.49	224.95
5	Pb ₄	10.00	19.28	33.25	41.09	5.18	108.88
6	Pb ₅	21.03	1.90	3.48	27.18	1.21	54.80

BDL- Below detection limit, Pb- Lead.

Table 1 revealed that the soil spiked with 1000 mg/kg of lead nitrate has the highest fraction value in exchangeable, carbonate, Fe-Mn, Organic matter and Residual compared to other spiked soils in decreasing order of the spiked

soil while Organic matter has the highest fraction value hence, this study revealed the strong affinity between organic matter and lead (Pb).

Table 2: Result of fraction of soil spiked with cadmium nitrate.

S/N	SPIKED SOIL (mg/kg)	EXCHANGEABLE (ma/kg)	CARBONATE (mg/kg)	Fe-Mn OXIDE (mg/kg)	ORGANIC MATTER (mg/kg)	RESIDUAL (mg/kg)	TOTAL FRACTION (mg/kg)
1	Cd ₀	BDL	BDL	BDL	0.17	BDL	0.17
2	Cd ₁	54.60	395.10	100.28	98.15	216.73	864.86
3	Cd ₂	63.19	186.13	31.55	2.93	12.10	295.90
4	Cd ₃	14.25	158.60	11.64	1.69	3.87	190.05
5	Cd ₄	12.10	45.17	3.69	11.45	13.10	85.51
6	Cd ₅	2.63	28.95	11.28	2.93	5.79	51.58

BDL- Below detection limit, Cd- Cadmium

Table 2 revealed that soil spiked with 1000 mg/kg of cadmium nitrate has the highest fraction value in carbonate, Fe-Mn, Organic and Residual in decreasing order of spiked soil but in exchangeable, soil spiked with 500 mg/kg is

higher than soil spiked with 1000 mg/kg. Carbonate has the highest fraction value with respect to other fraction values, hence, these study revealed the strong affinity between carbonate and cadmium (Cd).

Table 3: Result of fraction of soil spiked with lead nitrate and cadmium nitrate for lead

S/N	SPIKED SOIL (mg/kg)	EXCHANGEABLE (ma/kg)	CARBONATE (mg/kg)	Fe-Mn OXIDE (mg/kg)	ORGANIC MATTER (mg/kg)	RESIDUAL (mg/kg)	TOTAL FRACTION (mg/kg)
1	S ₀	BDL	BDL	BDL	0.17	BDL	0.17
2	S ₁	98.70	145.23	219.87	310.45	192.36	966.61
3	S ₂	120.20	63.48	96.72	140.60	49.55	470.55
4	S ₃	62.00	48.75	19.30	95.10	40.11	265.26
5	S ₄	20.80	8.50	25.07	50.87	10.45	115.69
6	S ₅	30.80	2.45	1.72	30.50	0.20	65.67

BDL- Below detection limit, Cd (Cadmium) + Pb (Lead) = S

Table 3 revealed organic matter still has the highest fraction value with equal amount of in spiked soil.

Table 4: Result of fraction of soil spiked with lead nitrate and cadmium nitrate for cadmium.

S/N	SPIKED SOIL (mg/kg)	EXCHANGEABLE (ma/kg)	CARBONATE (mg/kg)	Fe-Mn OXIDE (mg/kg)	ORGANIC MATTER (mg/kg)	RESIDUAL (mg/kg)	TOTAL FRACTION (mg/kg)
1	S ₀	BDL	BDL	BDL	0.17	BDL	0.17
2	S ₁	60.70	420.50	113.45	90.62	230.00	915.27
3	S ₂	40.80	126.52	51.84	9.72	15.85	244.27
4	S ₃	10.98	97.87	52.88	7.58	6.41	175.69
5	S ₄	18.26	40.00	11.20	19.02	4.67	93.15
6	S ₅	4.18	36.17	14.12	0.43	9.28	64.18

BDL- Below detection limit, Cd (Cadmium) + Pb (Lead) = S

Table 4 revealed carbonate still has the highest combination of lead nitrate and cadmium nitrate fraction value with the equal amount of in spiked soil.

Table 5: Result of the concentration of lead in the maize cob spiked with lead nitrate

S/N	SPIKED SOIL	Pb (mg/kg)
1	Pb ₀	BDL
2	Pb ₁	12.48
3	Pb ₂	10.63
4	Pb ₃	9.45
5	Pb ₄	10.48
6	Pb ₅	6.19

BDL- Below detection limit, Pb (Lead), Pb₀ is the control

Table 5 shows that maize plant is among several plant species that can hyper-accumulate soluble lead (Pb) in the soil like *Sesbonia Drummondii*, *Sevrerai Brassica*, *Piptathertan Miiacetall* (Sahi, *et al.*, 2002, Wong, *et al.*, 2001, Garcia, *et al.*, 2004). This study revealed that maize cob can accumulate lead (Pd) which is against the suggestion of Kumer, *et al.*, 1995 that lead (Pb) is relatively insoluble.

Table 6: Result of the concentration of cadmium in cadmium in the maize cob spiked with cadmium nitrate.

S/N	SPIKED SOIL	Cd (mg/kg)
1	Cd ₀	BDL
2	Cd ₁	0.94
3	Cd ₂	0.88
4	Cd ₃	0.07
5	Cd ₄	0.05
6	Cd ₅	0.04

BDL- Below detection limit, Cd (Cadmium), Cd₀ is the control

Table 6 revealed the concentration of cadmium in the maize cob hence, this study shows that maize plant can be used as a hyper-accumulator of cadmium as also reported by the hyper-accumulation of Cadmium (Cd) in *Arabidopsis* (Cosio, *et al.*, 2004 and Kupper, *et al.*, 2000), though *B. Juncea* accumulated more Cd due to its larger size (Ebb, *et al.*, 1997). Cosio, *et al.*, 2005 demonstrated that 35% Cd taken up accumulated in the cell wall/apoplast in *T. Caerulescens* leaves and hairy roots which appeared to be localized in the cells (Boominahan and Doran 2000). Cd uptake is likely mediated through transporters or channels for other divalent ions (Cosio, *et al.*, 2004, Karley, *et al.*, 2000)

Table 7: Result of the concentration of lead and cadmium in the maize cob spiked with lead and cadmium nitrate.

S/N	SPIKED SOIL	Pb (mg/kg)	Cd (mg/kg)
1	(Pb + Cd) ₀	BDL	BDL
2	(Pb + Cd) ₁	7.07	0.43
3	(Pb + Cd) ₂	6.92	0.42
4	(Pb + Cd) ₃	6.67	0.26
5	(Pb + Cd) ₄	4.19	0.37
6	(Pb + Cd) ₅	5.30	0.41

BDL- Below detection limit, Cd (Cadmium) and Pb (Lead)

Table 7 shows the concentration of lead (Pb) in maize cob was higher than Cadmium (Cd) uptake which was supported by the experiment done by Benjamin, *et al.*, 1980 which was based on the fact that addition of lead (Pb) decreases the adsorption of Cadmium (Cd). Zinc ca also reduce Cadmium uptake in many plant species (Lombi, *et al.*, 2001a and 2002a.).

Table 8: Result of physical- chemical properties of the soil sample.

S/N	PHYSICAL-CHEMICAL PARAMETERS	RESULTS
1	Ph	5.8
2	Organic Carbon Content (%)	2.8
3	P (mg/kg)	14.80
4	Na (mg/kg)	0.93
5	N (%)	0.7
6	K (mg/kg)	0.45
7	Ca (mg/kg)	6.91
8	Mg (mg/kg)	3.17
9	Sand (%)	87.40
10	Silt (%)	8.49
11	Clay (%)	4.11

Na- Sodium, Mg- Magnesium, P- Phosphorus, K- Potassium, Ca- Calcium, N- Nitrogen.

The summation of the values of Na, k, Mg, Ca will give CEC (Cation Exchangeable Capacity) value. Cation Exchange Capacity (CEC) (Henry, 2000, Barker, *et al.*, 1990 and McNeil, *et al.*, 2000).

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{CEC} &= \text{Na} + \text{K} + \text{Mg} + \text{Ca} \quad (1) \\
 &= 0.93 + 0.45 + 3.17 + 6.91 \\
 &= 11.46 \text{ Meq per } 100\text{g of soil}
 \end{aligned}$$

Table 8 revealed the value for the pH and Cation Exchange capacity (CEC) to be 5.8 and 11.46 Meq per 100g of soil respectively which shows that the solubility of metals in soil and ground water are predominantly controlled by pH and

This study revealed the knowledge on metal affinity to soil components and the strength with which they are bound to the matrix as shown by Narwal, *et al.*, 1999, the geochemical behavior of trace metals and their chemical form which was ascertained with the help of fractionation reveals that lead is strongly bound to the organic matter and weakly bound to the residual both within the soil treated with lead salt and combination of lead and cadmium salt. The effectiveness of the assisted bioremediation is

based on if the soil contamination is limited to within 3 feet of the surface, and if the ground water within 10 feet of the surface (Raskin, *et al.*, 1997 and Cunningham, *et al.*, 1997).

It has been reported that the potential mobility and bioavailability of heavy metal is influenced by whether the metals are added anthropogenically or present naturally in the soil (Narwal, *et al.*, 1999), however Sing and Steinnes, 1994 revealed that Cd and Zn of anthropogenic origin were more bioavailable than the naturally existing soil metals.

CONCLUSION:

The chemical fractionation of metals under study revealed the geochemical nature of two metals and their probable affinities with different chemical forms in soil spiked with different amount of lead (Pb) salt, cadmium (Cd) salt and combination of the two salts (Pb +Cd) indicate that lead (Pb) and cadmium (Cd) are strongly bound to organic and carbonate respectively which increases with the increase of the concentration of the metal used to spiked the soil. This study also revealed the promising potential for Pb and Cd phyto-extraction by maize cob not just maize root and shoot are able to absorb heavy metals due to transpiration.

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